

Canva-Aided Project-Based Learning to Improve Students' Writing Achievement

Khafit Royani¹, Muhammad Sukirlan², Ari Nurweni³

¹Student of Master of English Education, University of Lampung, Indonesia

^{2,3}Lecturer of English Education, University of Lampung, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This research aims to investigate the significant difference in the students' writing achievement and explore their perceptions on the project-based learning aided by Canva. The study employed a quantitative experimental method that the data were taken from pre-test and post-test of writing and students' perception questionnaire. The design of this research used one group pre-test and post-test design and the sample was taken randomly. The number of samples was 29 in one grade eleven class of Vocational School in Lampung Province, Indonesia. The data were analyzed statistically by using a paired sample test. The results demonstrated that the integration of Canva in project-based learning positively impacted students' writing achievement. The mean score of the pre-test was 63.62 and the post-test was 76.28. The gain between the mean score of pre-test and post-test was 12.655. In addition, the significance level was $0.000 < 0.05$. It means there was a significant difference between students' writing achievement in the pre-test and post-test. Besides that, the researcher also compared the t-value with the t-table. In this research, the t-value was $19.716 > 2.048$. It means that the implementation of Canva-aided project-based learning could improve the students' writing achievement. Regarding the students' perceptions, the use of Canva in language learning was dominantly positive, with many responses that Canva facilitated their expression of ideas and enhanced motivation in language learning.

In conclusion, this research highlights the potential benefits of using appropriate technology, such as Canva, to foster learning achievements in language education. Implementing Canva-aided project-based learning provided visually appealing support and encouraged students' creativity in expressing their ideas. The researcher suggests further integrating this technology into the language learning process to improve students' writing skills and overall learning motivation.

KEYWORDS: Canva, Project-Based Learning, Students' perceptions, Technology, Writing Achievement.

INTRODUCTION

According to Galko (2001), writing is a lifelong skill commonly used in education, the vocation, or for own personality. In other words, writing is one of the skills which exist all throughout our life. In addition, Leo (2007) said that writing involves the act of expressing ideas or thoughts through the use of words that are made in leisure time. Moreover, Barli (1995) told that writing is the best use of sentences to express a message. In similar words, writing is one of the ways to send information to the reader. The function of writing is the media for communicating our purpose to the reader.

Many reasons show that writing is essential in English. Brown (2004) said that four skills in English language teaching are considered to be the most important skill. These skills include listening, speaking, reading, and writing. It means that writing is one of the important skills in English language teaching. Therefore, the students learn and practice writing. Furthermore, Siahaan (2008) said that writing is a product of language skills which is written. It means that writing becomes an ability how people to communicate in the form of text.

Although previous research has emphasized the importance of writing skills in learning English, there are still some problems in students' writing achievement. According to Barli (1995), the common problem might be a lack of ability to construct grammatical sentences. Furthermore, Ekarista (2018) said that for students in Senior high school, writing looks very difficult because the students lack vocabulary and they do not have ideas in their minds, do not understand English grammar and also lack practice. It means that many students have some obstacles with grammatical errors when writing a sentence. Besides that, students do have not enough words and ideas to put in a sentence. So, the students are not interested in writing.

Then, project-based learning has recently been widely used to improve students' mastery of writing. According to Thomas (2000), project-based learning is a model that organizes learning around projects. Projects are complex tasks, based on challenging questions or problems that involve students in design, problem-solving, decision-making, or investigative activities; give students the opportunity to work relatively autonomously over extended periods of time. Furthermore, Hedge (1993) said that a project is an extended task that usually integrates language skills work through several activities. These activities combine in working towards an agreed goal and may include planning, the gathering of information through reading, listening, interviewing, etc., discussion of the information, problem-solving, oral or written reporting, and display.

Many studies have recently been undertaken with respect to the implementation of project-based learning for writing in a number of countries. For example in Iraq (Kavlu, 2017), in Malaysia (Sapan et al, 2019), and in Greece (Fragoulis, 2009). Almost all of the studies found that project-based learning had a statistically significant effect on writing.

However, the students have difficulties when they face complex projects. According to Thomas (2000), students have difficulties benefiting from self-directed situations, especially in complex projects. The difficulties are associated with initiating an inquiry, directing investigations, managing time, and using technology productively. This means that students often face difficulties when engaging in self-directed learning in complex projects. The mentioned challenges include initiating an inquiry, directing investigations, managing time, and using technology productively. The difficulties can hinder students' ability to benefit from self-directed learning experiences.

Based on the obstacles of the implementation of project-based learning above, the researchers use Canva as a digital media to overcome the problems. Canva is a digital medium that has several advantages. According to Utami and Djamhuri (2021), Canva is a twenty-first-century LMS: customizable, reliable, easy to use, and designed to help teachers and administrators reduce the time in their classrooms and institutions. In other words, when teachers and students use technology Canva media, they can save their time more efficiently because they can design the learning project easily. Besides that, the students also learn the technology productively in a complex project using Canva media which is familiar in this century.

Furthermore, Smaldino and Lowther (2015) stated that visuals in the classroom, including Canva, can serve multiple purposes, such as; 1) to make abstract ideas concrete; 2) to motivate students; 3) to give direct attention; 4) to repeat the information; 5) to recall previous knowledge; and 6) to reduce learning effort. In other words, Canva helps students in the learning process. Canva can help students who have difficulties visualizing abstract ideas become concrete ideas. So, the students can engage in self-directed inquiry. Furthermore, Canva provides more features that might the students get more information. So students can do a direct investigation dealing with formal invitations through Canva media.

Digital Canva media in project-based learning gives more interactive and creative teaching methods. However, it is important to understand how students perceive these media. According to Hafrizal et al (2021), perception shapes how learners react to learning, and it can be a determining factor between success and failure. Positive factors contribute to success in education, while negative factors contribute to failure. Therefore, understanding students' perceptions of digital media like Canva within project-based learning becomes essential for the researcher. By recognizing and addressing students' perceptions, educators can optimize the learning experience

The backgrounds above have motivated the researcher to conduct the research entitled Canva-aided project-based learning to improve students' writing achievement, in a setting where Canva is the tool or media for writing projects of a formal invitation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Writing

It has widely been accepted that writing is a productive skill in English. It is one of the important linguistic subjects. Siahaan (2008) said that writing is a skill of the writer to communicate information to a reader or group of readers. Moreover, Nunan (2003) said that writing is the physical act of committing words or ideas to some medium. On the other hand, writing is the mental work of inventing ideas, thinking about how to express them, and organizing them into statements and paragraphs that will be clear to a reader.

Writing is indeed a crucial skill that transcends various aspects of life, as noted by Bowker (2007). From casual communication like emails to more introspective practices such as journaling, writing serves as a medium for expression and reflection. In academic settings, as emphasized by Brown (2004), writing becomes indispensable for success, serving as a means for students to demonstrate

comprehension, critical thinking, and communication skills. It's not merely about passing a course but about developing the ability to articulate thoughts effectively, a skill that holds value beyond the classroom.

According to Byrne (1993), writing entails the encoding of a message, which essentially means translating our thoughts into language. It means that the process of writing involves transforming abstract ideas and concepts into a written form that can be understood by others. By selecting words, structuring sentences, and organizing ideas, we effectively convey our thoughts and communicate meaning through written language. In this way, writing serves as a means of externalizing and sharing our internal thoughts and experiences with others.

Based on the above definitions of writing, it can be concluded that writing is universally acknowledged as a vital skill in English, encompassing both the physical act of conveying information and the mental process of organizing ideas. Scholars emphasize its importance across various aspects of life, from personal reflection to academic success, highlighting its role in clear expression and communication. Through encoding thoughts into language, writing serves as a medium for sharing ideas and experiences effectively.

2.2. Measuring Writing

As asserted by Nunan (2003) writing is used to show that students have mastered a particular grammatical rule, rather than have a good idea about the subject matter. Correct spelling, grammar, and organization are the most important evidence of second language proficiency.

Another category of writing evaluation is presented by Brown (2004). Six general categories are often the basis of the assessment of student writing. Those are content, organization, discourse, syntax, vocabulary, and mechanics. In addition, Heaton (1998) said that writing skills are complex and sometimes difficult to teach, requiring mastery of grammatical and rhetorical devices and conceptual and judgmental elements. The following analysis attempts to group the many and varied skills necessary for writing good prose into five general components or main areas. Those are language use, mechanical skills, treatment of content, stylistic skills, and judgment skills.

Brown's and Heaton's aspects of evaluating writing are right to assess students' invitation letters. To assess the invitation letters, the researcher formulates some categories, namely, content, organization, language use, vocabulary, and mechanics. Those are described as follows:

- **Content:** involves the clarity and completeness of the information presented in the invitation letter. The information includes the date, time, place, theme of the event, and contact information where you can be contacted. Make sure all information is clear.
- **Organization:** evaluates the layout, arrangement of paragraphs, and the flow of thought in the invitation. A good invitation letter should have a well-organized structure, be easy to follow, and follow a common format for invitation letters.
- **Vocabulary:** is the choice of words and terms in the invitation letter that involves the use of words that are accurate, appropriate, and unambiguous. Good choice of words and terms must avoid excessive repetition and use the right words to describe the events or activities that are invited.
- **Language use:** is the use of appropriate, clear, and friendly assessment of correct and consistent use of grammar which includes the use of subject, predicate, and object, as well as the use of appropriate tenses, tenses, and sentence structure.
- **Mechanics:** involves an assessment of the correct and consistent use of spelling (such as writing the time format (AM/PM or 24 hours) must be written clearly and accurately) or, punctuation (such as periods, commas, colons, quotation marks, question marks, and exclamation points), capitalization (such as the use of capital letters at the beginning of sentences, titles, names of people or places, acronyms, and so on), and writing conventions (the use of correct numbers and symbols, use of known abbreviations or acronyms)

2.3. Process of Writing

In the context of writing, Richards and Renandya (2022) emphasized four fundamental stages: planning, drafting, revising, and editing. Additionally, three other stages-responding, evaluating, and post-writing-are imposed externally by the teacher. Harmer (2004) simplified the process into four elements: planning, drafting, editing, and producing the final version.

- **Planning** is the initial stage of the writing process, where writers contemplate the purpose, audience, and structural framework of their composition. This involves determining the objective or intention behind the writing, identifying the intended

readership, and outlining the overall organization or sequence of content within the piece. Effective planning sets the foundation for coherent and purposeful writing, guiding subsequent stages of drafting, revising, and editing.

- **Drafting** is the stage in the writing process where ideas are transformed into written form, typically representing initial thoughts that will undergo further development. Writers begin to articulate their ideas, composing sentences and paragraphs to convey their message. This phase allows for exploration and experimentation with language and structure, laying the groundwork for the subsequent refinement and revision of the written work.
- **Editing** is the stage in the writing process that follows drafting, during which writers meticulously review their work and make revisions to enhance clarity, coherence, and grammatical accuracy. This process involves scrutinizing the content for errors, inconsistencies, or areas that require improvement. Additionally, writers may seek feedback from others to gain fresh perspectives and identify areas for refinement. The goal of editing is to polish the draft, ensuring that it effectively communicates the intended message to the audience.
- **Producing the final version** is the concluding stage of the writing process, where writers ensure that their draft has been meticulously edited and refined. During this phase, writers carefully review their work, incorporating any necessary changes identified during the editing process. This may involve further revisions to improve clarity, coherence, and overall quality. The final version is meticulously crafted, and ready to be presented to readers with confidence in its effectiveness and impact.

By adhering to these stages, students can effectively create an invitation letter that is clear, engaging, and informative.

2.4. Project-Based Learning

Moss et al (1998) explained that project-based learning is an instructional method that immerses learners in real-world contexts by presenting them with meaningful problems or tasks to solve, or products to develop. This approach encourages active engagement and deeper understanding as students apply their knowledge and skills to authentic situations, fostering critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving abilities.

According to Bell (2010), project-based learning represents an innovative educational approach that imparts a diverse range of strategies crucial for success in the modern era. In this method, students take the reins of their learning through inquiry, actively engaging in the process of research and collaboration to develop projects that demonstrate their understanding. This approach not only fosters critical thinking and problem-solving skills but also encourages collaborative work and the application of knowledge in practical contexts, aligning with the demands of the twenty-first century.

According to Hamidah et al (2020), project-based learning is a teaching approach that focuses on assigning tasks, typically in the form of projects, to engage students in an inquiry process. This method involves providing students with opportunities to explore and investigate topics or problems, encouraging active learning and critical thinking. By emphasizing projects as the primary mode of instruction, project-based learning facilitates immersive learning experiences that promote inquiry and inquiry-based learning.

Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that project-based learning is an instructional approach that immerses students in real-world contexts by presenting them with meaningful problems, tasks, or projects to solve or develop. It emphasizes active engagement and deeper understanding as students apply their knowledge and skills to authentic situations. PBL fosters critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving abilities by encouraging students to explore, investigate, and collaborate on projects

2.5. Canva

According to Paula (2021), canva is recently made available to the public and offers a range of digital templates that users can utilize for different writing purposes. These templates cover various formats, including advertisements, resumes, and brief informational content. Moreover, Gehred (2020) said that canva is a graphic design tool founded in 2012 by Melanie Perkins, an Australian entrepreneur. It utilizes a drag-and-drop interface, making it user-friendly for both average users and design professionals. Canva offers a range of features including fonts, graphics, vectors, and templates, making it a versatile tool for creating various types of visual content.

The implementation of canva in learning writing has several advantages. Christiana and Anwar (2021) categorized that the functions and benefits of Canva into two categories: supplement and substitution. Supplement function, canva facilitates teachers in creating learning media and improves the online teaching process. Substitution function, canva improves learning media effectively, provides easy distribution of learning materials to students, and helps fulfill technology requirements.

From the explanation above, the writer believes that Canva as media that can improve writing teaching in educational environments. It is described as a versatile and user-friendly platform that offers a variety of templates and features, making it accessible to both educators and students. Using Canva to improve writing skills is seen as beneficial because it simplifies content creation, increases visual appeal and facilitates the process.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The design is a one-group pre-test-post-test design. According to Setiyadi (2018), the purpose of providing an initial test (T1) to the student in this design is to evaluate their initial competencies, while the ultimate goal of a final test (T2) is to evaluate the level of knowledge or skill that they have been acquired after undergoing a particular treatment. The subject of this research was the eleventh-grade students of Vocational School in Lampung Province, Indonesia. Then, the sample was one class from the eleventh grade which consists of 29 students. The researcher randomly selected the sample. The researcher used a writing test to collect the data.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Result

4.1.1. The Improving of Students' Writing Achievement

Table 4.1. The Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Post_test	76.28	29	10.159	1.886
	Pre_test	63.62	29	8.550	1.588

The data presented in the table above reveals that before the intervention, the students achieved a mean pre-test score of 63.62, with a total of 29 students. After the implementation of Canva-aided project-based learning, the students' scores notably increased to 76.28. These findings suggest a substantial improvement in the students' writing achievement attributed to the utilization of Canva-aided project-based learning.

To gain more complete understanding of the improvement score from the pre-test to the post-test, the researchers used a paired sample T-test. It was used to determine whether the improvement score from the pre-test to the post-test was significantly increased. The following table shows the result of the paired sample test:

Table 4.2 Result of The Paired Sample Test

		Paired Differences			t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
					Lower	Upper	
Pair 1	Post_test Pre_test	12.655	3.457	.642	11.340	13.970	19.716 28 .000

The test results of the paired samples test showed that there was a difference between the post-test and pre-test mean values. This difference was indicated by a positive mean difference (12.655), which indicates that the mean post-test score (76.28) is higher than the average pre-test score (63.62). The 95% confidence interval also supported this conclusion because the Confidence Interval got beyond zero.

In addition, the significance level is (0.000). It means that the significance level is below 0.05. Besides that, the researcher also compared t-value with t-table. In this research, t-value was 19.716, while t-table was 2.048. If t-value > t-table, the result of this research was significant. Thus, it could be concluded that the treatment of canva-aided project-based learning which was carried out between the pre-test and post-test had a significant positive impact, which was reflected in the increase in the average score from the pre-test to the post-test.

4.2. Discussion

Based on the result of this research, there was a significant improvement in the students' writing achievement after the students were taught through canva-aided project-based learning. The results of the student's project in writing invitation letters indicate an improvement in students' writing achievement in various aspects, including content, organization, vocabulary, language use, and mechanics.

The improvement in the content aspect of writing occurred because project-based learning provided students with the opportunity to understand more about invitation letters. This process occurs when the teacher explains the material, when students understand the examples of formal invitation in other sources and also when the teacher asks basic questions that guide students in creating projects. The findings of this study support the conclusions drawn in previous research conducted by Sapan et al. (2019), which indicated that utilizing project-based learning greatly enhances students' language proficiency. Specifically, in this study, students observed a notable improvement in their English speaking and writing skills as a result of engaging in project-based language learning.

When students make invitation letters, Canva also plays a role in improving the content aspect of writing. It involves the development of ideas through personal experience. Smaldino et al., (2015) stated that visuals in the classroom, including Canva, can serve to create concrete abstract ideas; 2) to motivate students; 3) to give direct attention; 4) to repeat the information; 5) to remember prior knowledge; and 6) to make learning effective. In this study, the students are allowed to read examples of formal invitations that are widely available on Canva. So, Students can use the same expressions when they create their invitation.

Meanwhile, in the language and vocabulary aspects, there was also an increase due to the implementation of project-based learning and the use of Canva. Project-based learning allows students to work in groups so that students can exchange information and give each other opinions. The most important thing is that students read examples on Canva, how words are written, and how phrases and sentences are formed. According to Suwanto (2021), the implementation of Canva in project-based learning can enrich their knowledge in the form of vocabulary, terms, or expressions.

There are also improvements in the design and mechanical aspects. Project-based Learning gives students the flexibility of time to complete their projects. Students can work on every detail of their project carefully. Furthermore, Canva also provides many invitation letter templates which are a factor in improving the quality of invitation letters from design and mechanical aspects. Since mechanics are included in the area of language features, this finding is in line with previous research conducted by Syarifah (2019) stated that the implementation of project-based learning develops some aspects including understanding the topic, the purpose, the text structure, and the linguistic features

CONCLUSION

The implementation of Canva-aided project-based learning to improve student's writing achievement could encourage and facilitate this collaborative process by allowing students to share and provide feedback on each other's work. So, students can improve their writing achievements through the use of language, vocabulary, and mechanisms through peer interaction. Additionally, Canva provides visual examples and templates for various writing tasks, such as invitation letters. Visual aids, such as Canva, can also help students understand concepts more effectively, improving their understanding of content and organization in writing.

REFERENCES

1. Bell, S. (2010). Project-based learning for the 21st century: Skill as for the future. *The Clearing House: A Journal of Educational Strategies, Issues and Ideas*, 83(2), 39-43. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00098650903505415>
2. Bowker, N. (2007). *Academic writing: A guide to tertiary level writing*. Massey University. <http://www.massey.ac.nz>
3. Brown, H. D. (2004). *Teaching by principles: An interactive approach to language pedagogy*. Longman.
4. Byrne, D. (1993). *Teaching writing skill*. Longman. <https://www.scribd.com/document/229219346/Byrne-D-1988-Teaching-Writing-Skills>
5. Christiana, E. and Anwar, K. (2021). The perception of using technology canva application as a media for english teacher creating media virtual teaching and english learning in Loei Thailand. *Journal of English Teaching, Literature, and Applied Linguistics*, 5(1), 62-69. <http://dx.doi.org/10.30587/jetlal.v5i1.2253>
6. Ekarista, F. (2018). Improving students' writing ability in recount text using picture series. *KnE Social Sciences*, 3(4), 343-351.

7. Fragoulis, I. and Tsiplakides, I. (2009). Project-based learning in the teaching of english as a foreign language in Greek Primary Schools: From theory to practice. *English Language Teaching*, 2(3), 114-115. <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v2n3p113>
8. Galko, F. (2001). *Better Writing Right Now*. Learning Express. https://images.collegedunia.com/public/college_data/images/entrance/entrance_brochure/1636979260Better%20Writing%20Ebook%20%E2%80%93%20Francine%20D.Galko.pdf
9. Gehred, A. P. (2020). Canva. *Journal of the medical library association*, 108(2), 338-340. <https://doi.org/10.5195/jmla.2020.940>
10. Hafrizal., Iskandar. U.K. and Samad. A. (2021). Students' Perception toward English Subject and Their Learning Outcome. *English Education Journal*, 12(3), 477-495. <https://doi.org/10.24815/eej.v12i3.19251>
11. Hamidah, H., Rabbani, T. A. and Fauziah, S. (2020). *HOTS-Oriented module; project-based learning*. SEAMEO QITEP in Language. <http://repositori.kemdikbud.go.id/id/eprint/21381>
12. Harmer, J. (1998). *How to teach english*. Longman. <https://ia800801.us.archive.org/31/items/HowToTeachEnglish/How%20to%20Teach%20English%20Harmer%2C%20Jeremy.pdf>
13. Heaton, J. B. (1998). *Writing English language test*. Longman. <https://octovany.files.wordpress.com/2013/12/ok-writing-english-language-tests-j-b-heaton.pdf>
14. Hedge, T. (1993). Key concept in EFL: Project work. *ELT Journal*, 47(3), 237-277. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/elt/47.3.275>
15. Kavlu, A. (2017). Implementation of project-based learning (PBL) in EFL (English as a foreign language) classrooms in Fezalar Education Institutions (Iraq). *International Journal of Sociaand Carol & Educational Studies*, 4(2), 67-79. <http://dx.doi.org/10.23918/ijsses.v4i2sip67>
16. Moss, D. and Carol, V.D. (1998). *Project-based learning for adult English*. ERIC Publications. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED427556>
17. Nunan, D. (2003). *Practical English language teaching*. McGraw-Hill Education.
18. Paulia, Q. (2021). Teaching Writing Through Canva Application at MTS Al-Islamiah Ciledug. *SELL*, 6(1), 95-101.
19. Richards, J. C. and Renandya, W. A. (2022). *Methodology in language teaching*. Cambridge University Press.
20. Sapan, N. S., Katijah, S., Zuhaini, N. A., Aishah, S. N. and Ramli, S. A. (2019). Project-based learning and its effect on student's English skills. *International Journal of Educationand Pedagogy*, 1(2), 74-86. <http://myjms.moe.gov.my/index.php/ijeap>
21. Setiyadi, B. (2018). *Metode penelitian untuk pengajaran bahasa asing*. Graha Ilmu.
22. Siahaan, S. (2008). *The English paragrah*. Graha Ilmu.
23. Smaldino, S. E., and Lowther, D. L. (2015). *Instructional technology and media for learning*. 5(3), 1-22
24. Sugiono. (2012). *Metode penelitian pendidikan*. Alfabeta.
25. Syarifah, E. F., & Emiliasari, R. N. (2018). Project-based learning to develop students' ability and creativity in writing narrative story. *Indonesian EFL Journal*, 5(1), 85- 94. <https://doi.org/10.25134/iefj.v5i1.1627>
26. Thomas, J. W. (2000). *A review of research on project-based learning*. The Autodesk Foundation. http://www.bie.org/research/study/review_of_project_based_learning_2000
27. Utami, Y. and Djamdjuri, D. S. (2021). Students' motivation in writing class using of canva: Students perception. *English Journal*, 15(2), 83-92. <https://doi.org/10.32832/english.v15i2.5536>

Cite this Article: Khafit Royani, Muhammad Sukirlan, Ari Nurweni (2024). Canva-Aided Project-Based Learning to Improve Students' Writing Achievement. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 7(5), 2912-2918